

iodide formed during the reactions and hence to shift the reactions forward¹³.

The reductants, mercury(I), isonicotinic acid hydrazide, thiosemicarbazide, thiourea, phenol and aniline could only be determined by excess back titrations. A period of 5 min is needed for the completion of the oxidation in these cases.

All the reductants studied undergo the usual oxidation schemes reported earlier^{8,9,11}. As expected from their usual oxidation schemes, 1 equivalent of oxidant is consumed per mole of ferrocyanide and mercury(I); 2 equivalents for arsenic(III), antimony(III), tin(II), sulphite, ascorbic acid and hydroquinone; 4 equivalents for hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide and isonicotinic acid hydrazide (only the hydrazine parts are oxidised); 6 equivalents for thiocyanate, phenol and aniline; 8 equivalents for thiourea; 10 equivalents for thiosemicarbazide; and 24 equivalents for Reinecke's salt and mercury(II) tetrathiocyanates of cobaltate(II) and zincate(II). These three complex thiocyanates have four thiocyanate groups each.

As per the proposed oxidation schemes, arsenic(III) is oxidised to arsenic(V), antimony(III) to antimony(V), tin(II) to tin(IV), mercury(I) to mercury(II), ferrocyanide to ferricyanide, sulphite to sulphate, ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid, hydroquinone to quinone, and phenol and aniline are tribrominated in presence of potassium bromide. The following equations show the modes of oxidation of other reductants, viz., thiocyanate and its three complexes, hydrazine and its two derivatives, semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide and thiourea.

DIH has got definite advantages over earlier developed dichloramine-T, dibromamine-T and chlorbromamine-T. Thiocyanate and the three complex thiocyanates studied here could be determined by direct potentiometric titrations using DIH, whereas these could be determined by excess back titrations using dichloramine-T, dibromamine-T, and chlorbromamine-T. This added reactivity of DIH helps to determine more reductants by direct titration methods.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.P.R.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. C. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 239.
2. C. G. R. NAIR, R. LALITHAKUMARI and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 525.
3. C. P. K. PILLAI and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1980, **27**, 751.
4. K. D. MAHILAMONY and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1981, **28**, 627.
5. M. P. RADHAMMA and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1983, **30**, 49.
6. P. INDRASENAN and M. P. RADHAMMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 729.
7. R. A. CORRAL and O. O. ORAZI, *Anales Asoc. Quim. Argentina*, 1956, **44**, 11 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, **51**, 2751).
8. T. J. JACOB and C. G. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 347.
9. V. R. NAIR and C. G. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1973, **20**, 696.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1964.
11. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. III.
12. M. P. RADHAMMA and P. INDRASENAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 239.

Extractive Microdetermination of Chromium(VI) with N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic Acid

S. B. GHOLSE*

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur-440 010
and

B. K. DESHMUKH and P. J. ANOKAR

Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 18 October 1982, revised 14 August 1983, accepted 25 March 1984

SEVERAL reagents have been employed for the solvent extraction studies of chromium(VI)¹⁻⁸. However, these methods suffer from many disadvantages. They need critical control of acidity, large volume of the organic phase, longer time for equilibration and are deficient at microgram level of chromium. Tributyl phosphate⁹ was also used for the extraction of Cr(VI) but the complex was found to be unstable. Extraction of Cr(VI) with long chain amines was also reported¹⁰, but had very low molar absorptivity ($\epsilon = 20 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Gallacetophone oxime¹¹ is a new spectrophotometric reagent used for the determination of Cr(VI). The molar absorptivity of this method ($\epsilon = 3.6 \times 10^3$) is about ten times smaller than that of the present method ($\epsilon = 3.4 \times 10^4$). Recently Cr(VI) has been extracted with tetraphenylarsonium chloride¹². But this method suffers from the disadvantage that anions like MnO_4^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ interfere in the determination.

In the present communication a new reagent N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) is used for extraction of Cr(VI). A yellow coloured

complex is extracted in carbon tetrachloride from sulphuric acid medium. It is possible to extract Cr(VI) in the presence of most of the commonly associated elements. The method is simple and rapid and can be employed for the determination of chromium in standard steel samples.

Experimental

Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz cells and a Ganson shaker were used.

TMBHA was synthesized as reported earlier^{1a}. Fresh solution of about 0.001 M TMBHA in carbon tetrachloride was used. A stock solution of Cr(VI) was prepared dissolving potassium chromate in water free from any reducing agent ($\sim 1.865 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$). It was standardized gravimetrically as the lead chromate^{1a}. The dilute solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution.

An aliquot of solution containing less than 16 μg of Cr(VI) was taken. Sulphuric acid and water were added to make the acidity 2.7 M and the solution was made to 10 ml. It was then shaken (10 min) with the solution of TMBHA ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, 10 ml) in carbon tetrachloride. The yellowish organic phase was separated and measured spectrophotometrically at 370 nm against a similarly processed reagent blank.

Application of the method : Samples of BCS steel were procured from the Bureau of Analysed Samples, Ltd. 0.1 g steel sample was treated with 50 ml 25% H_2SO_4 and heated gently until hydrogen evolution ceased. The flask was removed, content was cooled and H_2O_2 (100 vol) added dropwise to oxidize any carbon or carbide residue. The solution was boiled gently to destroy excess H_2O_2 , cooled and made up to 100 ml with water. Chromium was determined from this solution as mentioned in the general procedure.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of Cr-TMBHA complex : The absorption spectra of the complex ($\text{Cr} = 5.2 \mu\text{g}$) shows maximum absorption at 370 nm. The molar absorptivity at 370 nm is $3.4 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0015 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Effect of acids : The extraction behaviour of the complex was studied using hydrochloric and sulphuric acids. It is found that sulphuric acid gives intense colouration and the extraction is quantitative at 2.7 M concentration. The presence of ten times excess of TMBHA is sufficient for optimum extraction. The extraction is quantitative with 10 min equilibration and the colour of the extracted complex is stable for 4 h.

Beer's law and optimum range : The Cr(VI)-TMBHA complex system obeys Beer's law over the concentration range 0.10-1.60 μg of Cr(VI) per ml of carbon tetrachloride at 370 nm. The optimum

working range for photometric determination is 0.25-1.10 μg of Cr(VI) per ml of carbon tetrachloride.

Effect of chromium ion concentration and various solvents : The study of the effect of chromium ion concentration on the extraction at different acidity ruled out the possibility of polymerisation of the extractable species in the range of metal concentration 0.1-3.0 μg per ml.

Various solvents such as benzene, toluene, hexane, cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, *iso*-amyl alcohol, *iso* butanol, *n*-hexanol were tried for the extraction. It is found that carbon tetrachloride and chloroform are most suitable for clear phase separation and quantitative extraction of the complex.

Effect of diverse ions : The interference of several ions on the extraction behaviour of Cr(VI) was studied. The tolerance limit was calculated as the amount to cause $\pm 5\%$ error in the recovery of chromium. The results indicate that hundred times excess of Cl^- , Br^- , SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, MnO_4^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, citrate and tartrate do not interfere. The ten times excess of I^- and five times excess of NO_2^- are tolerable while NO_3^- interferes seriously. The hundred fold excess of Al^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , In^{3+} , and ten fold excess of Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , and Ce^{4+} do not interfere. Nb^{5+} , Ta^{5+} and Ti^{4+} in equal amount are tolerated while V^{5+} interferes seriously.

Precision and accuracy : Fifteen solutions of $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ Cr(VI) at 2.7 M sulphuric acid concentration in 10 ml were extracted with 10 ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ TMBHA and absorbance measured at 370 nm. It is found that the mean absorbance is 0.340 ± 0.05 . The relative mean deviation is $\pm 2.83\%$ and standard deviation is $\pm 1.15\%$.

The method is rapid, simple and permits separation and determination of chromium at tracer levels.

Application to alloy steels : The method has been applied successfully to three BCS steel samples. The average of a number of determinations from different samples are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF APPLICATION OF THE METHOD IN STEEL SAMPLES

Samples	Cr%	
	found	present
High speed steel (No. 241/2)	5.25	5.35
Alloy steel (No 60b)	0.70	0.75
Stainless steel (No. 69a)	17.90	18.40

References

1. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1959.
2. C. DEPTULA and K. MOSZYN'SKA, *Chemia Analit.*, 1968, 13, 211.

3. A. A. YADAV and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 290.
4. V. M. SHINDE and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1970, 249, 239.
5. W. M. MCNABB and J. F. HAZEL, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 27, 405.
6. W. J. MAECK, M. E. KUSSY and J. E. REIN, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 199, 69.
7. M. N. SASTRI and D. S. SUNDER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1967, 225, 56.
8. G. B. FASOLO, R. MALVRANO and A. MASSAGLIA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, 29, 569.
9. D. G. TUCK, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 27, 296.
10. J. ADAM and R. PRIBIL, *Talanta*, 1971, 18, 91.
11. P. NAGESWARA RAO and K. ADINARAYANA REDDY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 402.
12. N. K. BAISHYA and G. BARUAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 389.
13. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 581; 1971, 48, 753.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1962.

Separation and Microdetermination of Nitrate with *N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic Acid* (TMBHA)

S. B. GHOLSE*

Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur-440 010
and

B. K. DESHMUKH

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University,
Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 18 October 1982, revised 24 August 1983,
accepted 25 March 1984

NITRATES find their way in water from various sources¹. The presence of excess of nitrates in water causes pollution². Thus, determination of nitrates in water in micro-amounts is essential from the pollution point of view. Several methods have been suggested for the determination of nitrate in water³⁻⁹. Most of the colorimetric determinations are based on the conversion of nitrate in the presence of sulphuric acid into the nitro derivative of phenolic compounds.

In this communication, *N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid* (TMBHA) is proposed for the determination of nitrate in water. The method is based on the extraction of yellow coloured compound formed between nitrate and TMBHA in carbon tetrachloride. The coloured organic layer is measured at 360 nm. The reaction is very sensitive for nitrate determination. Nitrate is clearly separated from various other ions.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were done in Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer with 10

mm matched silica cells. Standard stock solution of potassium nitrate containing 6.2 μg nitrate per ml was prepared in deionized water.

The reagent, TMBHA, was synthesized and purified as reported earlier¹⁰. $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of TMBHA in double distilled carbon tetrachloride (carbon disulphide free) was prepared. Analytical grade sulphuric acid was used.

An aliquot containing less than 12.4 μg nitrate and 5.0 ml 7.2 *M* sulphuric acid was made to 10 ml and allowed to cool to room temperature. This solution was equilibrated with 10 ml $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMBHA in carbon tetrachloride for 20 min. The organic layer was collected over anhydrous sodium sulphate and measured at 360 nm against similarly processed reagent blank. The extracted nitrate was determined from the calibration curve.

Application of the method: Water from different local sources was collected. Pretreatment of this water for preparing sample solution was done by standard methods⁹. Water sample was evaporated to an appropriate volume and filtered. 2 ml of this sample solution was taken and nitrate content was determined as mentioned in the general procedure.

Results and Discussion

The yellow coloured extractable species formed between nitrate and TMBHA absorbs maximum at 360 nm.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.08-1.24 μg nitrate per ml with an optimum range 0.09-0.93 μg of nitrate per ml of carbon tetrachloride. The molar absorptivity was $8.0 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity was estimated to be 0.0008 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

The effect of acidity was studied over the range 0.1-10.0 *M* sulphuric acid. The colour intensity increases above 2.0 *M* acidity and attains maximum at 3.6 *M*. Beyond 3.6 *M* the absorbance remains constant, but the separation of two layers becomes difficult. Hence, all the measurements were carried out at 3.6 *M* acidity. 10 ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ TMBHA was adequate for quantitative extraction of 3.1 μg of nitrate. The absorbance of the complex remained constant for 2 h. A period of 10 min was sufficient for complete extraction.

Effect of foreign ions: The effect of various foreign ions on the extraction behaviour of 3.1 μg nitrate was studied. The tolerance limit was set at the amount of foreign ion to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of the nitrate. The results show that fifty fold excess of Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , As^{3+} , As^{5+} , Mo^{6+} , twenty times excess of Cu^{2+} , and five times excess of Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} do not interfere. Cr^{3+} , Cr^{6+} and W^{6+} are tolerated upto two times excess. BO_3^{3-} and NO_2^- interfere seriously. Fifty times excess of Cl^- , Br^- and ten times excess of I^- do not interfere.